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Technology Implementation Model and Architectural Patterns for CEI Use Cases

White paper

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1. Introduction and Approach

This white paper presents a technical implementation model and architectural patterns identified for Europe's Cloud-Edge-IoT (CEI) market.

1.1 Considered Use Cases

The UNLOCK-CEI team has analysed a large set (63) of use cases, in five major industry sectors, that appear promising for the Cloud-Edge-IoT market in Europe. This set of use cases (the "Considered Use Cases", see Table 1) was initially explored through a survey of 700 industry respondents, the results of which can be found in D1.21.

Some use cases identified in D1.2 have been subdivided into specific "use case solutions" to reflect different aspects of the overall use case that must be modelled differently, either because they involve different types of assets in different quantities and ratios or combine different architectural patterns that require different technical components. These use case solutions are included in Table 1 and assigned Use Case Codes that are consistent with the starting, undifferentiated use case. For example, Hospital Asset Tracking (H02) has been subdivided into three use case solutions, one for each of "dumb assets" (H02.1), "patient monitors" (H02.2), and "other high-value assets" (H02.3), since the costs of tracking devices for each asset type, and the quantities involved differ between the three use case solutions, affecting the functional requirements, implementation and market calculations.

In this white paper, the UNLOCK-CEI team examines each of the Considered Use Cases through a detailed structural analysis methodology. Each use case is categorised according to its possible architectural approaches for implementation, and common service requirements are identified for key architectural patterns. In total the original 63 Use Cases presented in D1.2 have been expanded to a list of 79 Use Cases and Use Case Solutions, which form the "Considered Use Cases" that are the foundation of this analysis.

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1 <https://zenodo.org/records/8107103>

Table 1: Considered Use Cases

Use Case Code	Generic Use Case	Use Case (from D1.2 Section 4)	Explanatory title
Agriculture			
A01.1	Employee Location Tracking	Employee safety monitoring	Track Employees in Hazardous Environments
A01.2	Employee Health Monitoring	Employee safety monitoring	Monitor Employee "Vitals" in Hazardous Environments
A01.3	Hazard monitoring	Employee safety monitoring	Monitor Conditions at Known Hazardous Locations
A02.1	Fixed Equipment Condition monitoring	Asset condition monitoring	Monitor the Condition of Key Fixed Equipment
A02.2	Fixed Equipment Predictive maintenance	Asset monitoring & maintenance	Predictive Maintenance for Key Fixed Equipment
A02.3	Mobile Equipment Condition Monitoring	Asset condition monitoring	Monitor the Condition of Key Mobile Equipment (e.g. tractors, trucks, harvesters)
A02.4	Mobile Equipment Predictive maintenance	Asset monitoring & maintenance	Predictive Maintenance for Key Mobile Equipment (e.g. tractors, harvesters)
A03	Product Inspection	Visual inspection - quality/integrity	Inspect agricultural products (e.g. at harvesters, and grading stations) for quality control
A04	Fixed Video surveillance	Video security & surveillance	Visual monitoring of fields and buildings
A05	Asset command & control	Asset command & control	Command & Control of Key Assets (e.g. processing machines)
A06	Field Condition monitoring	Agriculture Field Monitoring	Monitor the Condition of Farm Fields, Paddocks and Pasture areas
A07	Fleet Tracking	Asset location tracking	Track and Optimise Key Mobile Assets (e.g. tractors, harvesters)
A08	Process automation/ optimization	Process automation & optimization	Manage & Optimise precision agriculture systems
A09	Livestock Health Monitoring	Livestock monitoring	Collect Livestock health Data from "wearable" devices
A10	Livestock Tracking	Agriculture Animal Tagging	Track Livestock locations from "wearable" devices
A11	Autonomous Vehicles	Autonomous Vehicles	Enhancing and optimising the production
A12	Smart Building	Smart building	Smart Building Management
Energy			
E01.1	Employee Location Tracking	Employee safety monitoring	Track Employees in Hazardous Environments
E01.2	Employee Health Monitoring	Employee safety monitoring	Monitor Employee "Vitals" in Hazardous Environments

Use Case Code	Generic Use Case	Use Case (from D1.2 Section 4)	Explanatory title
E01.3	Hazard monitoring	Employee safety monitoring	Monitor Conditions at Known Hazardous Locations
E02	Movable Asset Tracking	Asset location tracking	Track the Location of Key Movable (portable) Assets (e.g. high-value test equipment and tools)
E03	Fixed Equipment Condition Monitoring	Asset monitoring & maintenance	Monitor the Condition of Key Fixed Equipment
E04	Fleet tracking	Fleet tracking	Track and Optimise Key Mobile Assets (e.g. repair trucks)
E05	Asset Command & Control	Smart meters	Smart Meters: Load Management, Theft Prevention
E06	Operational Reporting	Regulatory compliance	Operational Reporting for Regulatory Compliance
E07.1	Operational Monitoring	Remote network mgmt (e.g. fault detection)	Enhanced Grid Monitoring
E07.2	Operational Diagnostics	Remote network mgmt (e.g. fault detection)	Diagnostics, Incident detection from Enhanced Grid Monitoring
E08	Fixed Equipment Predictive maintenance	Sensor-based diagnostics & maintenance	Predictive Maintenance for Key Fixed Equipment (e.g. transformers, circuit breakers)
E09	Fixed Video surveillance	Video security & surveillance	Intrusion Detection & Access Control
E10	Asset command & control	Asset command & control	Asset Dispatch of Generation Assets, Command & Control of Key Assets
E11	Process automation/ optimization	Process automation & optimization	Smart Grid: Real-Time Analytics and Dynamic Grids Optimisation
E12	Drone-based inspection	Drone-based observation	Drone-based Inspection (e.g. remote generation, transmission assets)
E13	Technician monitoring	Field service technician monitoring	Technician Performance and Work Order Optimisation
E14	Process automation/ optimization	Connected drilling & extraction	Optimised Gas & Petroleum Exploration and Production
E15	Smart Building	Smart building	Smart Building Management
E16	Automated guided vehicles	Automated guided vehicles (AGVs)	Automated Guided Vehicles in Special Environments (switchyards, substations)
Healthcare			
H01	Remote Patient Monitoring	Remote Health Monitoring	Collect Patient Health Data from remote devices (e.g. in patients' homes)
H02.1	Movable Asset Tracking	Hospital Asset Tracking - dumb assets	Track Location of portable Assets (e.g. wheelchairs, hospital beds)
H02.2	Movable Asset Tracking	Hospital Asset Tracking - patient monitors	Track Location of smart Assets (e.g. bedside monitors)

Use Case Code	Generic Use Case	Use Case (from D1.2 Section 4)	Explanatory title
H02.3	Movable Asset Tracking	Hospital Asset Tracking - other high-value assets	Track Location of other high-value portable Assets (e.g. dialysis machines, imaging machines)
H03	Fixed Video surveillance	Video security & surveillance	Intrusion Detection & Access Control
H04	Operational Reporting	Regulatory compliance	Operational Reporting for Regulatory Compliance
H05	Hospital Patient Monitoring	Bedside Telemetry	Collect Patient Health Data from distributed devices in the hospital
H06	AI analysis & recommendations	AI-enabled Diagnosis & Treatment	Collect data about pathologies and symptoms to analyse and leverage cures.
H07	Robots or AR- assisted surgery	Robots or augmented-reality-assisted surgery	Routine surgical procedures are assisted by robots and/or AR tools for surgeons
H08	Smart Building	Smart building	Smart Building Management
H09	Automated guided vehicles	Automated guided vehicles (AGVs)	Automated Guided Vehicles (medical supplies, specimens) in hospitals
Manufacturing			
M01.1	Fixed Equipment Condition Monitoring	Asset monitoring & maintenance	Monitor Condition of Key Fixed Equipment
M01.2	Fixed Equipment Predictive maintenance	Asset monitoring & maintenance	Predictive Maintenance for Key Fixed Equipment
M02.1	Employee Location Tracking	Employee safety monitoring	Track Employees in Hazardous Environment
M02.2	Employee Health Monitoring	Employee safety monitoring	Monitor Employee "Vitals" in Hazardous Environments
M02.3	Hazard monitoring	Employee safety monitoring	Monitor Conditions at Known Hazardous Locations
M03	Product Inspection	Visual inspection - quality/ integrity	Inspect manufactured products at various stages of production for quality control
M04	Process automation/ optimization	Manufacturing operations/ automation	Manage & Optimise Smart manufacturing at a single facility
M05	Fixed Video surveillance	Video security & surveillance	Intrusion Detection & Access Control
M06	Product Asset Tracking	Food traceability	Track flow of food products through the agricultural food chain
M07	Asset command & control	Asset command & control	Command & Control of Key Assets (e.g. conveyor belts)
M08	Fleet tracking	Fleet tracking	Track and Optimise Key Mobile Assets (e.g. forklifts)
M09	Operational Reporting	Regulatory compliance	Operational Reporting for Regulatory Compliance

Use Case Code	Generic Use Case	Use Case (from D1.2 Section 4)	Explanatory title
M10	Process automation/ optimization	Process automation & optimization	Manage & Optimise Smart manufacturing across the enterprise
M11	Smart building	Smart building	Smart Building Management
M12	Movable Asset Tracking	Asset location tracking	Track Location of Key Movable (portable) Assets (e.g. Pallets, Crates, Boxes, high value test or calibration equipment)
M13	Automated guided vehicles	Automated guided vehicles (AGVs)	Automated Guided Vehicles in Factories, Warehouses
Transport			
T01.1	Employee Location Tracking	Employee safety monitoring	Track Employees in Hazardous Environment
T01.2	Employee Health Monitoring	Employee safety monitoring	Monitor Employee "Vitals" in Hazardous Environments
T01.3	Hazard monitoring	Employee safety monitoring	Monitor Conditions at Known Hazardous Locations
T02	Fleet tracking	Fleet tracking	Track and Optimise Key Mobile Assets (e.g. trucks, containers, ships, railroad cars)
T03	Passenger Tracking	Passenger traffic flow	Track passenger flow across the transport network to manage capacity and congestion
T04	Fixed Video surveillance	Video security & surveillance	Intrusion Detection & Access Control
T05	Drone-based inspection	Vehicle & infrastructure inspection	Drone-based Inspection (e.g. railroad rights of way, switchyards)
T06	Operational Reporting	Regulatory compliance	Operational Reporting for Regulatory Compliance
T07	Movable Asset Tracking	Freight monitoring	Track Location of Key Movable (portable) Assets (e.g. Containers, Pallets, Crates, Boxes)
T08.1	Mobile Equipment Condition Monitoring	Asset monitoring & maintenance	Monitor Condition of Key Mobile Equipment (e.g. trucks, containers, ships, railroad cars)
T08.2	Mobile Equipment Predictive maintenance	Asset monitoring & maintenance	Predictive Maintenance for Key Mobile Equipment (e.g. trucks, containers, ships, railroad cars)
T09	Autonomous Vehicles	Autonomous Vehicles	Autonomous vehicles leveraging security in a controlled system
T10	Product Inspection	Quality of shipment conditions	Inspect shipping units (containers, pallets, crates, boxes) to detect damage and ensure proper routing
T11	Asset command & control	Asset command & control	Command & Control of Key Assets (e.g. close/open doors to warehouses for truck access)

Use Case Code	Generic Use Case	Use Case (from D1.2 Section 4)	Explanatory title
T12	Automated guided vehicles	Automated guided vehicles (AGVs)	Automated Guided Vehicles in railyards, ports, warehouses
T13	Smart building	Smart building	Smart Building Management

1.2 Structural Analysis Assumptions and Methodology

The approach begins with several key framing assumptions, which in turn support the step-by-step methodology employed. These framing assumptions are:

- ☁ The enterprise, its facilities and the “targets” (i.e. the trucks or livestock, or employees to be tracked, controlled or monitored) of each use case are the units of analysis for each use case.
- ☁ There is a common technical approach that can be used to model the implementation, and the economics, of all the use cases.
- ☁ Functional requirements can be modelled by functional components deployed at specific points in the technical model. These functional components can be identified, and their costs estimated, to enable the calculation of typical system costs and corresponding overall market opportunity.
- ☁ The technical model is enhanced with estimates of the scale and speed of processing and computation required to implement each Use Case, as well as the physical scope of the Use Case implementation.
- ☁ There are a small number of common architectural patterns needed for use case implementation.

These assumptions are explored in sequence in sections 2-4, supporting the presentation of the technical model, functional requirements, and identified architectural patterns. In section 5, the initially identified architectural patterns are validated against the practical experience of the MetaOS use cases.

2. The Enterprise, Facility, and Targets as Units of Analysis

Each use case is considered as an independent technology application implemented at a single facility. While similar applications implemented at multiple facilities, and at multiple enterprises, may enable new functions and create new value, the initial implementations must be justified by the value – and return on investment – generated for the initial adopting facility or enterprise.

The “target” of each use case is an important factor in modelling technology solutions:

- ⦿ The number and nature of the Use Case target are critical: fixed, mobile or movable (mobile but not self-propelled), diversity of target types, economic value of the Use Case for different target types (e.g. location tracking of hospital beds probably does not have the same ROI for location tracking of high-value assets like dialysis machines).
- ⦿ The complexity of Devices needed to capture information about, or control, each Target object.
- ⦿ The relationship between the Target object and the related Device: e.g. retrofit vs. “integrated” by the original manufacturer of the Target (e.g. condition monitoring for an agricultural machine, such as a tractor, where tractor manufacturers are adding value to their products by making them “smart”).

Understanding, much less quantifying, the circumstances that would justify investment in each use case is outside the scope of this analysis. Instead, it is assumed that some number of enterprises, as defined by available statistics, will have both reasons for investing in each use case and the financial and technical capacity to do so.

1. The enterprise is a key unit of analysis since detailed statistics are available across Europe on the number of enterprises in each economic sector, large enough (based on employees, revenue, livestock, value-added, etc.) to be able to justify the investment.
2. Many enterprises have multiple facilities. For each use case, conservative assumptions about the average number of facilities per enterprise can be developed.
3. The number of “targets” of each Use Case – the object in the real world being tracked, monitored or controlled – can also be estimated conservatively based on real-world experience and/or published statistics (e.g. the total number of cattle held by farms of a certain size, divided by the number of farms of that size).

Estimates of enterprises, facilities and targets for each use case in each industry sector are presented in other outputs of the UNLOCK-CEI project.

3. Common Technical Model

The common technical model includes several basic components, the scale and speed of computation and processing required for the Use Case, and the physical scope of the Use Case. These aspects are described below.

3.1 Basic Components

The common technical model used in this White Paper builds on the “continuum computing concept” presented in “Developing a Reference Architecture for the Continuum - Concept, Taxonomy and Building Blocks”², illustrated in Figure 1:

Figure 1: Components of the Continuum Computing Concept

This technical model guides the structural analysis as follows:

- ⦿ The analysis starts with the “target” of each Use Case – the object in the real world being tracked, monitored or controlled.
- ⦿ The nature of the target and the objectives of the Use Case drive requirements for the *Sensors* and/or *Actuators* with which that object must be equipped. (Note: *Sensors* and *Actuators* are generically referred to as *Devices* in this White Paper.) *Devices* are packaged appropriately for the circumstances of the facility and the use case.
- ⦿ Most data flows from *Devices* are gathered or disseminated by *Gateway* components. For most Use Cases only one *Gateway* component is required at the facility, although, for Use Cases with wider physical scopes, such as Smart Meters and Smart Grid, additional *Gateways* would be needed.
- ⦿ For most Use Cases, data storage and computation can be performed by either or both *Edge Computing* or *Cloud Computing* capabilities. Where low latency computation is required, near-edge computation may be appropriate, but the specifics may be determined as much by the evolution of the edge computing market and related business models in different geographic areas as by technical requirements.

2 <https://zenodo.org/records/8403593>

- ☁ In general, the *Gateway* would implement various functions for triggering data-driven actions, ranging from alerts to employees in unsafe conditions, grading of agricultural produce, and maintenance activities, to command and control of production equipment and overall management of facility operations, working in conjunction with suitable *Edge Computing* or *Cloud Computing* capabilities.

The concept of a facility-based central capability is used only to organise the analysis. For each use case, there are a range of feasible implementation approaches appropriate to the architectural pattern of the use case (see next section). At the same time, taking a facility-based design approach establishes the conditions against which cloud-centric architectures must compete.

For example, the assumption that each facility requires a central Gateway does not require the physical installation of such a gateway, although this is one architectural approach. Alternatively, data might be gathered from distributed devices using a public communications network (such as a 5G mobile network) and then sent to cloud-based “gateway software” for processing and storage.

3.2 Scale and Speed of Communications and Processing

This technical model, which describes the main components of the solution for each Use Case and their relationships or “topology”, is enhanced with several other factors assessed for each Use Case:

- ☁ **Message Size:** Complexity of the data collected by/sent to the *Devices*. This is referred to as the message size and measured in bytes, to the nearest order of magnitude, e.g. from 10 Bytes for a message providing the location of a Target, to 1 Gigabyte (1 billion bytes) for a message describing energy grid status and conditions. This value is estimated based on the nature of the Use Case.
- ☁ **Message Frequency:** Frequency of messages sent to/received from each *Device*. This is referred to as the message frequency and measured in messages per second, to the nearest order of magnitude, e.g. from 0.0001/second (one message every 10,000 seconds – roughly 10 times per day), to 1,000/second for high criticality, low latency applications. This value is estimated based on the nature of the Use Case.
- ☁ **Device Fanout:** The number of *Devices* connected to each *Gateway*. This factor affects the communication capabilities required for the *Gateway*, as well as the computational and storage requirements of the associated *Edge* and *Cloud Computing* capabilities. As with the other factors, this is estimated to the nearest order of magnitude (ranging between 10 and 10,000 – with the highest device fanout expected for smart grid Use Cases in energy). Unlike the factors above, this value must be estimated based on market conditions (e.g. on average, how many heads of cattle per farm will be tracked in a livestock tracking Use Case), but results from that analysis (to be presented in a separate White Paper) are used for this analysis.
- ☁ **Device Diversity:** the number of distinct kinds of *Devices* connected to each *Gateway*. As with Device Fanout, this factor affects the computational and storage requirements of the associated *Edge* and *Cloud Computing* capabilities, since increased device diversity requires separate processing for each device type (which might involve different message formats and/or messaging protocols, each with its processing overheads), as well as additional functionality for managing the registration of different device types with each Gateway. As with the other factors, this is estimated to the nearest order of magnitude (ranging between 10 and 1,000 – with the highest device diversity expected for condition monitoring in the manufacturing and energy sectors).

These factors contribute to several derived factors that drive functional requirements for each

Use Case implementation:

☁ Total Gateway Data rate (bytes/s): This is the product of Message Size, Message Frequency, and Device Fanout.

☁ Total Device Data rate (bytes/s): This is the product of Message Size and Message Frequency.

Required data rates for *Gateways* and *Devices*, respectively, are assumed to drive networking costs for both kinds of components. Additional networking costs, also related to required data rates, will be required for communication across more challenging physical scopes (see next section).

Certain Use Cases require additional computational and processing capabilities from *Edge Computing* or *Cloud Computing* components.

A few Use Cases also appear to benefit from portable packaging for the *Gateway* as well as the *Devices* attached to *Targets*.

3.3 Physical Scope of Use Case

The final dimension of the common technical model is the physical scope of the Use Case – that is, over what physical area will the Use Case operate? Where are the Target objects to be monitored? Where will the *Gateway* device be located?

Use Cases can be grouped into five common physical scope patterns consistent with the kinds of facility where the use cases would be implemented. These patterns are as follows:

1. Limited Area
2. Indoors
3. Right-of-way physical scope
4. Broad service area scope
5. Universal service scope

While most discussions of “edge” and “IoT” assume that these capabilities might be made available across wide geographic areas (e.g. an entire city or country), many of the use cases examined here do not require this. Instead, for many of the use cases analysed here, the physical scope of interest is a Limited Area that matches that of the facility itself – the farm, vineyard, factory, railyard, port area, or hospital. This more concentrated physical scope makes it feasible and practical to provide those use cases’ gateway capability in a physical system located at the facility itself. This type of scope allows short-range networking technologies, such as LPWan, to be used instead of more expensive wide-area networking approaches such as 4G LTE, 5G or eventually 6G.

Some Limited area physical scopes are complicated by the fact that the Use Case must be implemented Indoors: inside one or more buildings, where internal construction (aluminium and steel structures and cladding, masonry) interferes with radio communications (including 5G/6G) and requires additional investment in repeaters with wired connections, etc.

There are several other important physical scope patterns found for the use cases under consideration:

☁ Service corridor scopes: This physical scope pattern applies to use cases implemented along major roads, pipelines, electric transmission lines, railroad tracks, etc. Here there is no convenient location for a single gateway capability. However, the physical topology of these use cases can easily accommodate hierarchical networking approaches (e.g. all data is collected from a single railroad track, then shared with a higher-level system for multiple tracks), possibly leveraging existing network infrastructure available to the enterprise. Alternatively, the use of public networking capabilities (e.g. 5G) and public or private cloud

may be as, or more, effective than a hierarchical approach.

- ☁ Service area scopes: This pattern matches the common conception of Edge-IoT applications, with data-gathering devices distributed across a wide area, requiring the use of public network technologies (both wired and wireless). Examples include:
 - ☁ At-home health monitoring, across the service area of a hospital or regional health authority,
 - ☁ Smart grid applications, across the service area of an electrical power distribution operator.
- ☁ Universal scope: This pattern is primarily driven by business-to-consumer (“B2C”) use cases, compared to the business-to-business (“B2B”) use cases that represent the bulk of the use cases under consideration.

For both service corridor and service area scope patterns, use case implementations immediately face the question of timing and availability – when will the required networking and distributed edge processing capabilities be available throughout the service corridors or service areas of interest? Use case rollouts will be limited by the availability of these technologies, or implementing enterprises will need to make their own investments to meet these requirements.

Use Cases operating indoors, or in service corridors/areas are assumed to require additional networking capabilities, which in turn depend on required data rates for the *Gateways* and *Devices*, respectively.

3.4 Summary of Aspects of Common Technical Model

Table 2 presents the factors above for each of the Considered Use Cases.

Use Case Code	Explanatory title	Message Size (Bytes)	Message Frequency (message/s) frequency	Fanout (Devices per Gateway)	Gateway Bandwidth (Bytes/s)	Device Bandwidth (Bytes/s)	Device Diversity	Physical Scope	Actuation	Portable	Regulated	Advanced Processing
A01.1	Track Employees in Hazardous Environment	1E+01	1E+00	1E+01	1E+02	1E+01	10	Limited area (Farm)	Y	Y	Y	
A01.2	Monitor Employee "Vitals" in Hazardous Environments	1E+03	1E+00	1E+01	1E+04	1E+03	10	Limited area (Farm)	Y	Y	Y	
A01.3	Monitor Conditions at Known Hazardous Locations	1E+02	1E+00	1E+01	1E+03	1E+02	10	Limited area (Farm)		Y	Y	
A02.1	Monitor Condition of Key Fixed Equipment	1E+02	1E-04	1E+01	1E-01	1E-02	10	Limited area (Farm)				
A02.2	Predictive Maintenance for Key Fixed Equipment	1E+02	1E-04	1E+01	1E-01	1E-02	10	Limited area (Farm)				Y
A02.3	Monitor Condition of Key Mobile Equipment (e.g. tractors, trucks, harvesters)	1E+02	1E-04	1E+01	1E-01	1E-02	100	Limited area (Farm)				
A02.4	Predictive Maintenance for Key Mobile Equipment (e.g. tractors, harvesters)	1E+02	1E-04	1E+01	1E-01	1E-02	100	Limited area (Farm)				Y
A03	Inspect agricultural products (e.g. at harvesters, grading stations) for quality control	1E+06	1E+01	1E+01	1E+08	1E+07	1	Limited area (Farm)	Y			Y
A04	Visual monitoring of fields and buildings	1E+06	1E-02	1E+01	1E+05	1E+04	1	Limited area (Farm)				
A05	Command & Control of Key Assets (e.g. processing machines)	1E+03	1E+01	1E+01	1E+05	1E+04	10	Limited area (Farm)				Y
A06	Monitor Condition of Farm Fields, Paddocks and Pasture areas	1E+02	1E-04	1E+01	1E-01	1E-02	10	Limited area (Farm)				
A07	Track and Optimise Key Mobile Assets (e.g. tractors, harvesters)	1E+01	1E-01	1E+01	1E+01	1E+00	10	Limited area (Farm)				
A08	Manage & Optimise precision agriculture systems	1E+06	1E+00	1E+01	1E+07	1E+06	1	Limited area (Farm)	Y			Y

Use Case Code	Explanatory title	Message Size (Bytes)	Message Frequency (message/s) frequency	Fanout (Devices per Gateway)	Gateway Bandwidth (Bytes/s)	Device Bandwidth (Bytes/s)	Device Diversity	Physical Scope	Actuation	Portable	Regulated	Advanced Processing
A09	Collect Livestock health Data from “wearable” devices	1E+02	1E-04	1E+02	1E+00	1E-02	10	Limited area (Farm)				
A10	Track Livestock locations from “wearable” devices	1E+01	1E-03	1E+03	1E+01	1E-02	1	Limited area (Farm)				
A11	Enhancing and optimising the production	1E+08	1E+03	1E+01	1E+12	1E+11	1	Limited area (Farm)	Y			
A12	Smart Building Management	1E+04	1E-02	1E+01	1E+03	1E+02	1	Limited area (Farm)	Y			
E01.1	Track Employees in Hazardous Environment	1E+01	1E+00	1E+01	1E+02	1E+01	10	Service Area (distributed)	Y		Y	
E01.2	Monitor Employee “Vitals” in Hazardous Environments	1E+03	1E+00	1E+01	1E+04	1E+03	10	Service Area (distributed)	Y		Y	
E01.3	Monitor Conditions at Known Hazardous Locations	1E+02	1E+00	1E+01	1E+03	1E+02	10	Indoor area (hospital & campus)			Y	
E02	Track Location of Key Movable (portable) Assets (e.g. high value test equipment and tools	1E+01	1E-01	1E+03	1E+03	1E+00	10	Service Area (distributed)				
E03	Monitor Condition of Key Fixed Equipment	1E+02	1E-03	1E+02	1E+01	1E-01	1,000	Service Area (distributed)				
E04	Track and Optimise Key Mobile Assets (e.g. repair trucks)	1E+01	1E-01	1E+02	1E+02	1E+00	10	Service Area (distributed)				
E05	Smart Meters: Load Management, Theft Prevention	1E+02	1E-03	1E+04	1E+03	1E-01	10	Service Area (distributed)	Y		Y	Y
E06	Operational Reporting for Regulatory Compliance	1E+06	1E-04	1E+01	1E+03	1E+02	1	Service Area (distributed)			Y	
E07.1	Enhanced Grid Monitoring	1E+09	1E+03	1E+02	1E+14	1E+12	100	Service Area (distributed)				
E07.2	Diagnostics, Incident detection from Enhanced Grid Monitoring	1E+09	1E+03	1E+02	1E+14	1E+12	1,000	Service Area (distributed)				Y
E08	Predictive Maintenance for Key Fixed Equipment (e.g. transformers, circuit breakers)	1E+02	1E-04	1E+01	1E-01	1E-02	1,000	Service Area (distributed)				Y
E09	Intrusion Detection & Access Control	1E+06	1E+00	1E+02	1E+08	1E+06	1	Service Area (distributed)				

Use Case Code	Explanatory title	Message Size (Bytes)	Message Frequency (message/s) frequency	Fanout (Devices per Gateway)	Gateway Bandwidth (Bytes/s)	Device Bandwidth (Bytes/s)	Device Diversity	Physical Scope	Actuation	Portable	Regulated	Advanced Processing
E10	Asset Dispatch of Generation Assets, Command & Control of Key Assets	1E+03	1E+01	1E+01	1E+05	1E+04	100	Service Area (distributed)			Y	Y
E11	Smart Grid: Real-Time Analytics and Dynamic Grid Optimisation	1E+07	1E+00	1E+03	1E+10	1E+07	1	Service Area (distributed)	Y			Y
E12	Drone-based Inspection (e.g. remote generation, transmission assets)	1E+06	1E+02	1E+01	1E+09	1E+08	1	Service Area (distributed)				
E13	Technician Performance and Work Order Optimisation	1E+02	1E-03	1E+02	1E+01	1E-01	10	Service Area (distributed)				
E14	Optimised Gas & Petroleum Exploration and Production	1E+08	1E+02	1E+03	1E+13	1E+10	1	Limited area (Exploration area)	Y			Y
E15	Smart Building Management	1E+04	1E-02	1E+02	1E+04	1E+02	1	Service Area (distributed)	Y			Y
E16	Automated Guided Vehicles in Special Environments (switchyards, substations)	1E+08	1E+03	1E+01	1E+12	1E+11	1	Service Area (distributed)	Y			
H01	Collect Patient Health Data from remote devices (e.g. in patients' homes)	1E+03	1E+00	1E+03	1E+06	1E+03	10	Service Area (distributed)			Y	
H02.1	Track Location of portable Assets (e.g. wheelchairs, hospital beds)	1E+01	1E-03	1E+03	1E+01	1E-02	1	Indoor area (hospital & campus)				
H02.2	Track Location of smart Assets (e.g. bedside monitors)	1E+01	1E-03	1E+03	1E+01	1E-02	1	Indoor area (hospital & campus)				
H02.3	Track Location of other high value portable Assets (e.g. dialysis machines, imaging machines)	1E+01	1E-03	1E+02	1E+00	1E-02	10	Indoor area (hospital & campus)				
H03	Intrusion Detection & Access Control	1E+06	1E+00	1E+02	1E+08	1E+06	1	Indoor area (hospital & campus)				
H04	Operational Reporting for Regulatory Compliance	1E+06	1E-04	1E+01	1E+03	1E+02	1	Indoor area (hospital & campus)			Y	

Use Case Code	Explanatory title	Message Size (Bytes)	Message Frequency (message/s) frequency	Fanout (Devices per Gateway)	Gateway Bandwidth (Bytes/s)	Device Bandwidth (Bytes/s)	Device Diversity	Physical Scope	Actuation	Portable	Regulated	Advanced Processing
H05	Collect Patient Health Data from distributed devices in the hospital	1E+02	1E+00	1E+03	1E+05	1E+02	10	Indoor area (hospital & campus)				
H06	Collect data about pathologies and symptoms to analyse and leverage cures.	1E+06	1E-04	1E+01	1E+03	1E+02	1	Indoor area (hospital & campus)			Y	Y
H07	Routine surgical procedures are assisted by robots and/or AR tools for surgeons	1E+08	1E+03	1E+01	1E+12	1E+11	1	Indoor area (hospital & campus)	Y		Y	
H08	Smart Building Management	1E+04	1E-02	1E+02	1E+04	1E+02	1	Indoor area (hospital & campus)	Y			Y
H09	Automated Guided Vehicles (medical supplies, specimens) in hospitals	1E+08	1E+03	1E+01	1E+12	1E+11	1	Indoor area (hospital & campus)	Y			
M01.1	Monitor Condition of Key Fixed Equipment	1E+02	1E-03	1E+02	1E+01	1E-01	1,000	Indoor area (Factory and yard)				
M01.2	Predictive Maintenance for Key Fixed Equipment	1E+02	1E-04	1E+01	1E-01	1E-02	1,000	Indoor area (Factory and yard)				Y
M02.1	Track Employees in Hazardous Environment	1E+01	1E+00	1E+01	1E+02	1E+01	10	Indoor area (Factory and yard)	Y		Y	
M02.2	Monitor Employee "Vitals" in Hazardous Environments	1E+03	1E+00	1E+01	1E+04	1E+03	10	Indoor area (Factory and yard)	Y		Y	
M02.3	Monitor Conditions at Known Hazardous Locations	1E+02	1E+00	1E+01	1E+03	1E+02	10	Indoor area (Factory and yard)			Y	
M03	Inspect manufactured products at various stages of production for quality control	1E+06	1E+01	1E+01	1E+08	1E+07	1	Indoor area (Factory and yard)	Y			Y
M04	Manage & Optimise Smart manufacturing at a single facility	1E+07	1E+02	1E+01	1E+10	1E+09	1	Indoor area (Factory and yard)	Y			Y

Use Case Code	Explanatory title	Message Size (Bytes)	Message Frequency (message/s) frequency	Fanout (Devices per Gateway)	Gateway Bandwidth (Bytes/s)	Device Bandwidth (Bytes/s)	Device Diversity	Physical Scope	Actuation	Portable	Regulated	Advanced Processing
M05	Intrusion Detection & Access Control	1E+06	1E-02	1E+02	1E+06	1E+04	1	Indoor area (Factory and yard)				
M06	Track flow of food products through the agricultural food chain	1E+01	1E-03	1E+03	1E+01	1E-02	1	Agricultural Value Chain				
M07	Command & Control of Key Assets (e.g. conveyor belts)	1E+03	1E+01	1E+01	1E+05	1E+04	100	Indoor area (Factory and yard)				Y
M08	Track and Optimise Key Mobile Assets (e.g. forklifts)	1E+01	1E-01	1E+01	1E+01	1E+00	10	Indoor area (Factory and yard)				
M09	Operational Reporting for Regulatory Compliance	1E+06	1E-04	1E+01	1E+03	1E+02	1	Indoor area (Factory and yard)				
M10	Manage & Optimise Smart manufacturing across the enterprise	1E+07	1E+00	1E+01	1E+08	1E+07	1	Indoor area (Factory and yard)	Y			Y
M11	Smart Building Management	1E+04	1E-02	1E+02	1E+04	1E+02	1	Indoor area (Factory and yard)	Y			Y
M12	Track Location of Key Movable (portable) Assets (e.g. Pallets, Crates, Boxes, high value test or calibration equipment)	1E+01	1E-03	1E+03	1E+01	1E-02	1	Indoor area (Factory and yard)				
M13	Automated Guided Vehicles in Factories, Warehouses	1E+08	1E+03	1E+01	1E+12	1E+11	1	Indoor area (Factory and yard)	Y			
T01.1	Track Employees in Hazardous Environment	1E+01	1E+00	1E+01	1E+02	1E+01	10	Limited area (Transport facility)	Y		Y	
T01.2	Monitor Employee "Vitals" in Hazardous Environments	1E+03	1E+00	1E+01	1E+04	1E+03	10	Limited area (Transport facility)	Y		Y	

Use Case Code	Explanatory title	Message Size (Bytes)	Message Frequency (message/s) frequency	Fanout (Devices per Gateway)	Gateway Bandwidth (Bytes/s)	Device Bandwidth (Bytes/s)	Device Diversity	Physical Scope	Actuation	Portable	Regulated	Advanced Processing
T01.3	Monitor Conditions at Known Hazardous Locations	1E+02	1E+00	1E+01	1E+03	1E+02	10	Limited area (Transport facility)			Y	
T02	Track and Optimise Key Mobile Assets (e.g. trucks, containers, ships, railroad cars)	1E+01	1E-01	1E+03	1E+03	1E+00	10	Limited area (Transport facility), Corridor (rights of way)				
T03	Track passenger flow across the transport network to manage capacity and congestion	1E+06	1E+01	1E+03	1E+10	1E+07	1	Limited area (Transport facility) AND/OR Corridor (rights of way)				Y
T04	Intrusion Detection & Access Control	1E+06	1E+00	1E+02	1E+08	1E+06	1	Limited area (Transport facility), Corridor (rights of way)				
T05	Drone-based Inspection (e.g. railroad rights of way, switchyards)	1E+06	1E+02	1E+01	1E+09	1E+08	1	Limited area (Transport facility), Corridor (rights of way)				
T06	Operational Reporting for Regulatory Compliance	1E+06	1E-04	1E+01	1E+03	1E+02	1	Limited area (Transport facility), Corridor (rights of way)			Y	
T07	Track Location of Key Movable (portable) Assets (e.g. Containers, Pallets, Crates, Boxes)	1E+01	1E+00	1E+04	1E+05	1E+01	10	Limited area (Transport facility), Corridor (rights of way)				Y

Use Case Code	Explanatory title	Message Size (Bytes)	Message Frequency (message/s) frequency	Fanout (Devices per Gateway)	Gateway Bandwidth (Bytes/s)	Device Bandwidth (Bytes/s)	Device Diversity	Physical Scope	Actuation	Portable	Regulated	Advanced Processing
T08.1	Monitor Condition of Key Mobile Equipment (e.g. trucks, containers, ships, railroad cars)	1E+02	1E-04	1E+03	1E+01	1E-02	100	Limited area (Transport facility), Corridor (rights of way)				
T08.2	Predictive Maintenance for Key Mobile Equipment (e.g. trucks, containers, ships, railroad cars)	1E+02	1E-04	1E+03	1E+01	1E-02	100	Limited area (Transport facility), Corridor (rights of way)				Y
T09	Autonomous vehicles leveraging security in a controlled system	1E+08	1E+03	1E+02	1E+13	1E+11	1	Limited area (Transport facility), Corridor (rights of way)	Y		Y	
T10	Inspect shipping units (containers, pallets, crates, boxes) to detect damage and insure proper routing	1E+06	1E+01	1E+02	1E+09	1E+07	1	Limited area (Transport facility), Corridor (rights of way)	Y			Y
T11	Command & Control of Key Assets (e.g. close/open doors to warehouses for truck access)	1E+03	1E+01	1E+01	1E+05	1E+04	100	Limited area (Transport facility), Corridor (rights of way)			Y	Y
T12	Automated Guided Vehicles in railyards, ports, warehouses	1E+08	1E+03	1E+01	1E+12	1E+11	1	Limited area (Transport facility)	Y			
T13	Smart Building Management	1E+04	1E-02	1E+02	1E+04	1E+02	1	Limited area (Transport facility), Corridor (rights of way)	Y			Y

3.5 Functional Components Required to Implement the Common Technical Model

This section translates the common technical model described above into functional components that can be combined to meet most of the functional requirements of the Considered Use Cases. Components are presented for *Gateways* and *Devices*, respectively. Codes are assigned to each component to simplify presentation of other aspects of the technical model.

3.5.1 Gateway Functional Components

Functional components required for *Gateways* are listed below along with their assigned codes:

- ☁ GBAS: Base Unit: Fixed or portable
- ☁ GDAT: Basic Message Processing (based on total gateway data rate)
- ☁ GADV: Advanced Processing and Computation (based on total gateway data rate – may be implemented in *Edge Computing* or *Cloud Computing* components depending on economics and business model)
- ☁ GNB: Basic Network Interface (assuming “Limited Area” physical scope, based on total gateway data rate)
- ☁ GNF: Additional Network Capabilities (for “Indoors”, “Service Corridor” and “Service Area” physical scopes, based on total gateway data rate)
- ☁ GCAP: Max Connected Devices (based on device fanout)
- ☁ GACT: Support for Device Actuation (based on device fanout)
- ☁ GREG: Support for Device Actuation in a Regulated Environment (based on device fanout)
- ☁ GDIV: Support for diverse connected devices (based on the number of device types required)

Detailed configuration codes and cost estimates are presented in Appendix X.

3.5.2 Device Functional Components

Functional components required for *Devices* are as follows:

- ☁ DBAS: Base Unit: Fixed or portable
- ☁ DDAT: Basic Message Processing (based on total device data rate)
- ☁ DNB: Basic Network Interface (assuming “Limited Area” physical scope, based on total device data rate)
- ☁ DNF: Additional Network Capabilities (for “Indoors”, “Service Corridor” and “Service Area” physical scopes, based on total device data rate)
- ☁ DACT: Support for Actuation
- ☁ DREG: Support for Actuation in a Regulated Environment

Detailed configuration codes and cost estimates are presented in Appendix 1.

4. Common Architectural Patterns Found Across Different Use Cases

The Use Cases considered in this analysis can be grouped into six main architectural patterns:

1. Location Tracking
2. Visual Inspection
3. Condition Monitoring
4. Predictive Maintenance and Operational Reporting
5. Asset Command and Control
6. Process Management and Autonomous Operations.

Each architectural pattern accommodates a range of use cases, which, despite superficial differences, can be seen to share a common architecture. For example, for Level 1 – “Location Tracking”, simple location information is gathered from a population of devices attached to the subject to be tracked, e.g. movable assets including livestock, fixed assets in some cases, as well as people (employees, or potentially passengers or customers). For all of these use cases, regardless of the specifics of industry or application, location data must be gathered from distributed devices via a communications network, stored and processed in a consistent fashion (which might be a central location, or a logically centralised application in the cloud), providing various outputs to various users and/or other IT (or OT) systems.

The different architectural patterns are numbered roughly from simplest to most complex. For example, Level 1 – “Location Tracking” – use cases are the simplest, with only location information collected from distributed devices. Level 3 – “Monitoring” – use cases are more complex, augmenting location information, with condition data gathered from the distributed devices. The L3 pattern complements and extends the L1 pattern. Similarly, each of the L4 (“Diagnostics”), L5 (“Command and Control”) and L6 (“Process Management”) use cases complement and enhance other use cases at a facility at a lower-numbered architectural pattern.

Figure 2 below illustrates the different architectural patterns, showing data flow directions, relative data volumes (e.g. thin arrows indicate small data volumes), etc.

Figure 2: Schematic illustration of architectural patterns

The sections below describe each architectural pattern in more detail. Use Case-specific requirements are described with a corresponding code for cross-referencing. Several service requirements are associated with the “shape” of the use cases within each category of pattern; specific requirements are identified and labelled in this section.

4.1 Location Tracking (Level 1 – “L1”)

Location Tracking use cases are the simplest, requiring only the collection of location information from distributed devices.

For use cases operating in limited physical scopes, e.g. farms, factories, railyards, etc., L1 use cases benefit from less expensive networking requirements. Use cases operating inside buildings, or across wider service territories, transport corridors, etc. will require more expensive networking requirements. Smart IT design can limit this requirement – for example, packages can be tracked at transport facilities using lower-cost networking, while between these facilities each package can be assumed to “stay put” and only the “carrying” equipment (container, railcar, lorry, etc.) would need to be tracked. (Such an approach would not identify situations where packages are stolen, nor would it support end-to-end freight monitoring.)

Gateway Service Requirements:

- ⬢ Location Tracking Capabilities have modest service requirements, generally requiring low-frequency (high latency – e.g. once every 10 minutes) message frequency, small message sizes, modest overall data collection bandwidth, and modest data analysis. Most data analysis requires mapping of measured locations to pre-existing facility maps or service territory maps (“Where are the railroad cars?”), and comparison with asset management data (“Where are the railroad cars SUPPOSED to be?”), with online data exploration, periodic reporting plus alerts for exceptions and anomalies. Advanced processing is generally not required.
- ⬢ Some use cases (e.g. Employee Location Tracking for safety monitoring) require faster data collection (e.g. once per minute) and alerts (actuation) of exposure or proximity to hazards. These analytics are also likely to require certification to comply with relevant employee safety regulations.

Device Service Requirements:

- ⬢ Location Trackers only need to report their location, keeping their costs low. Message size is also modest
- ⬢ Some L1 implementations involve a large number of location trackers in the Use Case, e.g. tracking the location of packages, crates, etc. in Use Case T07, which requires a low-cost device for the use case to be economically feasible. Such high quantities also enable economies of scale, which makes this requirement achievable, as well as synergies with similar use cases in the L1 category, further expanding the scale of production that might be possible.

The device “fanout” for employee safety monitoring use cases in most sectors is relatively low, which makes the combination of low-cost location trackers with a higher-cost central gateway uneconomic. Instead, such use cases would more effectively be designed with a higher cost employee tracking device, able to access wide area networking (such as 5G), combined with a lower cost gateway performing the required data analytics in the cloud. If a given facility invests in other CEI use cases that support on-premise data collection and analysis, the gateway capability could also shift to a more “classic” design to avoid recurring charges for cloud-based processing. (This assumes the more expensive wide-area capable location tracker could also connect to a local gateway. Moreover, it is expected that these devices will need to be replaced often since they are “wearable” and might be lost or damaged.)

Also, employee safety monitoring in several sectors (notably agriculture) could benefit from a “portable” gateway capability. In Agriculture, certain hazardous activities might be seasonal or linked to the operation of other equipment (e.g. farm machinery), so the central capability might again be provided by a portable unit that can be set up as needed.

4.2 Visual Inspection (L2)

Visual Inspection use cases mostly rely on the capabilities of the distributed devices, which are typically video cameras equipped with use-case-appropriate processing. Central capabilities may offload some video processing, to the extent this is possible in low-frequency (high latency) use cases.

Service Requirements:

Service requirements differ based on the generic use cases under consideration:

- Drone-based video collection must have weight and power characteristics consistent with operation onboard an unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) (DPROAE). Remote operator interfaces should support both integrated operation (drone operator is also the inspector), as well as two-person operation (DRONE1). Live feeds for both the operator and the inspector may require a relatively short range of operation (even at lower resolution), although longer range operation would be valuable (this requirement will benefit from military applications) (DRONE2). Storage of higher resolution video should be possible onboard, for access/download on landing, including detailed flight path information and aligned with “waymarks” and other operator annotations (“this looks bad – need to review high res video”) (SR-DPROAE). Video processing and image recognition can be applied to downloaded video (DRONE3) – but onboard processing and image recognition in selected sectors may be possible in the future (DRONE4).
- Video surveillance of property and assets is well established. Surveillance cameras can be combined with motion detection and/or image analysis, reducing the bandwidth required for communication with any central processing capability (SURVL1). Motion detection and/or image recognition can also be implemented centrally for collected video (SURVL2). Generally higher latency (low frequency) designs are feasible since adverse events do not occur rapidly.
- Product inspection use cases involve domain- or sector-specific image recognition capabilities, operating with low latency in order not to slow down activities at the facility (NSPCT1). Devices can link to actuators to allow for product grading (e.g. diversion of products into different product lines), marking, and interfaces with other OT systems (NSPCT2). Operator interfaces provide input (feature annotation) for model training and supervision (NSPCT3). Central capabilities might support federated learning and/or the sharing of new information with industry partners (NSPCT4). Product inspection use cases are usually low “fanout” applications, with a small number of inspection stations per facility, so most analytics capability should be located at the inspection device (NSPCT5), possibly supported by central capabilities hosted in the cloud or on general-purpose on-premise resources (NSPCT5).

4.3 Condition Monitoring (L3)

Condition Monitoring use cases are more complex, with more data gathered from each distributed device, which are then collected by the *Gateway* for analysis and reporting. The L3 pattern is similar to the L1 (“Location Tracking”) pattern but operates with a more diverse set of “targets” to be monitored (including employees, livestock, as well as both mobile and fixed assets). The corresponding condition data varies depending on the target, and some targets are themselves very diverse, e.g. lorries, railcars, manufacturing equipment, etc. Even common categories of

equipment, such as pumps used in different sectors, are themselves extremely diverse, with different kinds of condition monitoring data available.

Many Condition Monitoring use cases are often, but not always, complemented by Predictive Maintenance use cases in the L4 architectural pattern. Since the two patterns are not always present together, they are separated to highlight the architectural differences. For example, patient health monitoring data might be collected as a reference, but there is no corresponding “predictive maintenance” (diagnostic) use case – this is the responsibility of physicians at the hospital. Where D1.2 described a predictive maintenance use case, a corresponding condition monitoring use case has been added for consistent treatment.

L3 use cases operating in limited physical scopes, e.g. farms, railyards, etc., benefit from less expensive networking requirements. L3 use cases operating indoors, as well as across wider service territories, transport corridors, etc. will require more expensive networking capabilities.

Condition Monitoring generally requires low-frequency (high latency – e.g. once every minute) data collection, modest overall data collection bandwidth, and modest data analysis. Condition Monitors usually report a modest number (on the order of 10-20) of parameters about each target device. Most data analysis requirements are met by the corresponding Predictive Maintenance use case, or through communication of data to other systems or responsible personnel. This also applies to patient health monitors (at bedside or remotely) – telemetry of bedside monitoring in hospitals is not the primary mechanism for detecting problems (this is handled by the actual patient monitor), and, by definition, home health monitoring for chronic conditions or disabilities does not need to be rapid response (if it were, the patient would be in the hospital).

Gateway Service Requirements:

- ☁ Even within a single facility, each condition monitoring application may need to gather data from diverse condition monitors, with different data formats as well as communication protocols.
- ☁ Bedside Telemetry and Remote Patient Monitoring (in Healthcare) involve slightly higher aggregate data collection bandwidth and processing.

Device Service Requirements:

- ☁ Generally, the population of targets for condition monitoring per facility is not very large. Although low-cost devices are desirable, economies of scale may not be achievable. Manufacturing and Transportation are the exception to this, with up to 100 monitored devices per manufacturing facility, and up to 1,000 monitored devices per transportation facility, however, device diversity can also be high, increasing the challenges required to interface with such a range of devices.
- ☁ The role of OEMs is significant: condition data is sometimes already generated by the target asset – retrofit data collection can be difficult, and installing a retrofit condition monitor can also be difficult. Integration of condition monitors with new (or refurbished) assets is technically more attractive and more cost-efficient than retrofit. The marginal cost of OEM monitors is close to zero. Moreover, OEMs have better insight into what needs to be monitored and what monitoring results mean. At the same time, the adoption of OEM monitoring devices will primarily depend on the replacement cycle for the target assets (e.g. many farm tractors will be used for many years to come), which will slow adoption.

4.4 Predictive Maintenance and Operational Reporting (L4)

Predictive Maintenance use cases are assumed to enhance corresponding Condition Monitoring (L3) use cases. Implementations of L4 use cases involve the detailed analysis of condition monitoring data resulting in the generation of “conclusions” or “insights” that are translated in real-world actions by other systems (PREDMI). L4 use cases require central analysis capabilities

(software and underlying processing infrastructure) appropriate to the use case (PREDM2), but do not require additional investment in distributed devices for data collection, since they exploit the data collected from the devices deployed in the corresponding L3 use case.

Another group of use cases, grouped into the “L4” architectural pattern, addresses requirements for operational reporting and or regulatory compliance. Again, these use cases depend on data collected by other use cases operating at lower architectural levels (L3, as well as L2 and L1 use cases), and no investment in distributed devices is required.

Predictive Maintenance and Operational Reporting use cases do not directly “act” on data, conclusions or insights, instead, these are translated into a variety of forms that can be acted on by others:

- ☁ Support for a human user’s interactive exploration of target conditions (PREDM3), and generation of corresponding *ad hoc* or standardised reports (PREDM4),
- ☁ Generation of alerts through appropriate communication channels (PREDM5),
- ☁ Creation of work orders in maintenance systems that will prompt personnel to conduct diagnostic or maintenance activities (PREDM5).

Predictive Maintenance use cases are modelled as analytics capabilities implemented in software as part of the *Gateway* or in *Edge Computing* or *Cloud Computing* capabilities. This software can use rule-based technology to assess the condition of each monitored device (PREDM6), as well as data analytics to compare the health and performance of similar devices to find anomalies (PREDM7). These use cases can also leverage artificial intelligence tools to provide more useful conclusions, through several modes of operation:

- ☁ Implementation of machine learning model inferencing (PREDM8), based on models developed either by the enterprise, by a group of cooperating enterprises using the same equipment, and/or by the manufacturer of the devices analysed.
- ☁ Contribution of operational data to the training of such models (PREDM9), either directly through data sharing arrangements or indirectly through federated learning mechanisms.

Operational Reporting use cases operate in a similar fashion, implementing industry-standard interactive monitoring and reporting tools (OPRPT1) to allow enterprise personnel and other authorised individuals (such as regulatory authorities) to review the condition of a facility and including alerts triggered by operational thresholds set by enterprises and/or regulators (OPRPT2).

4.5 Asset Command and Control (L5)

While implementations of L4 use cases have no direct ability to execute actions determined by the data that is being collected, use cases at this architectural level, “Asset Command and Control”, model this capability explicitly. The degree of command and control of the target assets is assumed to be more limited than full control (full control use cases are categorised at the next architectural level (L6)). For example, if the target asset is a passenger car, L5 implementations might only be able to command that the car come to a safe stop as soon as possible, or possibly start the engine to warm up the car – there is no capability to drive the car or navigate open terrain.

This category includes three main sets of use cases

- ☁ Control of fixed assets such as conveyor belts, or other fixed machinery,
- ☁ Control of mobile assets where “full control” is still quite limited, e.g. for a locomotive which essentially can only be “commanded” to accelerate and brake, or a utility repair “bucket truck” controlling the swivel and elevation of the bucket,
- ☁ Control of customer appliances through smart meter applications. This is typically limited to disabling or enabling a given appliance (for example disabling high-energy clothes dryers

during periods of peak electricity demand) or setbacks to home heating thermostats or similar control devices.

As with L4 Operational Reporting, L5 use cases exploit data collected by other use cases operating at lower architectural levels (L3, as well as L2 and L1 use cases) (ACMD1). Required central processing and analytics depend strongly on the application and domain (ACMD2), but the cloud should not be the only location for data processing, since asset command and control can be time-sensitive and usually cannot tolerate the round-trip delays that might be added by cloud-hosted applications (ACMD3). Given the risks associated with faulty operation, associated central processing software will be expected to comply with relevant product safety regulations, including certification of software design and quality processes (ACMD4).

The distributed remote control devices that are required generally complement any devices gathering and transmitting condition-monitoring data. Since the suite of possible commands is limited, device complexity is lower, but reliability must be high, with redundancies and fail-safes built in (ACMD5). Separate devices may be required to achieve high levels of cybersecurity (ACMD6). Monitoring and control devices may be packaged together, but may still reflect segregated architectures to ensure both reliability and security (ACMD7). Given the risks associated with faulty operation, the design and manufacturing of these remote control devices will be expected to comply with relevant product safety regulations, including certification of design and manufacturing processes (ACMD8).

4.6 Process Optimisation and Autonomous Operations (L6)

Process Optimization and Autonomous Operations represent the top level (L6) of architectural patterns seen in the use cases considered in this analysis. They build on other use cases implemented at a facility (using the architectural patterns presented earlier) and generally integrate with other information technology (IT) and operations technology (OT) systems present across the enterprise.

Autonomous Operations include “autonomous vehicle” use cases discussed in the media, but limited to sector-specific applications:

- ☐ Transport: autonomously operated truck and rail freight, local logistics and delivery applications. Subject to safety regulations and public opinion, these applications may be limited to certain areas or rights-of-way.
- ☐ Agriculture: autonomously operated farm equipment (tractors, harvesters, sprayers, etc.) operating on private land, but sometimes travelling on local roads.

Automated Guided Vehicles limit operations to more restricted areas:

- ☐ Health: drug dispensing carts, mobile dialysis units, supply carts.
- ☐ Manufacturing: forklifts, supply carts, assembly transports.
- ☐ Energy: bucket trucks, and specialised repair equipment on site, but not operating on public roads.
- ☐ Transport: forklifts, cranes, rail yard switching engines.

Robotic surgery is also included in this category since it shares many architectural characteristics with autonomous operations use cases.

In all of these Autonomous Operation use cases, the following service requirements can be identified:

- ☐ Devices on each vehicle are comparable to systems required for a fully autonomous consumer vehicle, with camera systems, image recognition, rapid response rates, high aggregate data rates and on-device processing requirements, etc. (AUTON1). Generally overall quantities

projected are low, but will benefit from the broader autonomous vehicle market, so designs should be compatible with developments in that consumer market (AUTON2). Given the risks associated with faulty operation, the design and manufacturing of these devices will be expected to comply with relevant product safety regulations, including certification of design and manufacturing processes (AUTON3).

- ⦿ Requirements for robotic surgery systems will be different, but will still involve imaging systems, image recognition, rapid response rates, etc. (AUTON4). Parallels with the autonomous vehicle market are still possible and might be exploited for improved economics (AUTON5). At the same time, as a medical device, these systems will need to comply with relevant certification requirements and other regulations (AUTON6), which may make synergies with the autonomous vehicle market difficult.
- ⦿ With the more limited operating scope of these systems, facility-based support systems can offload certain “high latency” activities, reducing the demands on distributed devices. These systems must still be able to process high data rates, with some low-latency support activities still required (AUTON7). As with the devices themselves, given the risks associated with faulty operation, the design and manufacturing of these devices will be expected to comply with relevant product safety regulations, including certification of design and manufacturing processes (AUTON8). Additional requirements may apply to central systems supporting robotic surgery suites (AUTON9).

Two key types of Process Management and Optimisation use case are considered:

- ⦿ Broad process automation and optimisation across a facility or enterprise within a specific sector or domain. Sectoral use cases are considered for Agriculture, Energy, and Manufacturing, as well as one domain-specific application within the Energy sector automating oil & gas drilling and production operations.
- ⦿ More narrow “smart building” applications, applicable in all sectors, automating building operations to optimise worker safety and comfort, operating costs including energy consumption, GHG generation, etc.

In these use cases, the following service requirements can be identified:

- ⦿ Applications combine data from other use cases operating at lower architectural levels (L5 and below) as well as information technology (IT) and operations technology (OT) systems present across the enterprise (OPT11). This requirement is more pronounced for Process Management and Optimisation than for smart building use cases.
- ⦿ Additional remote control devices, typically automate low-sensitivity assets such as doors and gates (for both smart building applications and to enable the flow of goods within a facility) (OPT12).
- ⦿ Smart building use cases can benefit from broadly adopted central algorithms and software that can be configured to specific industrial facilities (OPT13).
- ⦿ More comprehensive automation and optimisation algorithms and software will be sector- or domain-specific (OPT14).
- ⦿ All of these central processing capabilities can be effectively hosted on-premise or in the cloud since there are few low latency requirements (OPT15).
- ⦿ Given the mission-critical nature of these applications, many enterprises will want to retain a high level of control over this software (OPT16).
- ⦿ Conversely, smart building applications are well suited to cloud-based solutions (OPT17).

5. Mapping Architectural Patterns to MetaOS Use Cases

In the previous section, we explored the architectural patterns defined in Section 5. Here, we evaluate how well these patterns cover the specific use cases presented by the MetaOS. We also consider the potential for identifying new patterns and highlight areas where the current set might be lacking. Table 3 synthesises the mapping of the MetaOS use cases, both to the Considered Use Cases presented in Table 1 (and analysed in WPI of the UNLOCK-CEI project) as well as to the six architectural patterns identified above.

Table 3: Mapping MetaOS Use Cases to Considered Use Cases and Preliminary Architectural Patterns

Use Case Name	Project	Sector	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	L6	L7	L8
Edge Computing Containers near Renewable Energy Sources	aerOS	E	-	-	E07.1	E07.2 E8	E05	E11	-	-
Connected and Cooperative Mobile Machinery focused on agriculture	aerOS	A	A07	-	A02.3	-	-	A11	-	-
Data-driven Cognitive Production Lines	aerOS	M	M12	-	-	-	-	M04	-	-
Smart Edge for the Port Continuum	aerOS	T	T02	T10	T08.1	T08.2	-	N/A	-	-
Energy Efficient, Health Safe & Sustainable Smart Buildings	aerOS	E	N/A	-	N/A	N/A	-	E15	-	-
Intelligent Power Grid	FLUIDOS	E	-	-	E03 E07.1	E07.2	-	E11	-	-
Smart Viticulture	FLUIDOS	A	-	A04	N/A	N/A	N/A	A11	-	-
Robotic Logistics	FLUIDOS	E	E04	N/A	N/A	N/A	-	E16	-	-
In-car Advanced Infotainment and Multimedia Management system (IAIMM)	ICOS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	N/A	-
Agriculture Operational Robotic Platform (AORP)	ICOS	A	-	-	-	-	N/A	A08	-	-
Railway Structural Alert Monitoring system (RSAM)	ICOS	T	-	-	N/A	T08.2	N/A	N/A	-	-
Energy Management and Decision Support system (EMDS)	ICOS	E	-	-	N/A	N/A	E05	-	-	-
Environment Crisis Management	NebulOus	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	N/A
Transportation and Logistics: Supply of Fresh Food to a City	NebulOus	T	T02	N/A	N/A	N/A	-	-	-	-
Smart City: Computer Vision for City Maintenance	NebulOus	-	-	A04	-	-	-	-	-	-
Energy and utilities: Windmill Maintenance	NebulOus	E	-	E12	-	E08	-	-	-	-
Agriculture: Precision agriculture	NebulOus	A	-	N/A	A06	N/A	-	A08	-	-

Use Case Name	Project	Sector	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	L6	L7	L8
Smart Farming and Precision Agriculture	NEMO	A	-	A03 A04	A06	-	L5	A08 A11	-	-
Smart Energy & Smart Mobility	NEMO	E	-	N/A	E07.1	N/A	E05	E11	-	-
Smart Manufacturing & Industry 4.0	NEMO	M	M02.1	-	-	-	M07	M04 M13	-	-
Smart Media / City & XR	NEMO	-	-	N/A	-	-	-	-	N/A	-
Energy Management in Smart Buildings/Cities	nephele	E	-	N/A	N/A	-	E05	E15	-	-
Smart Port	nephele	T	T02	T10	T08.1	-	N/A (T11)	-	-	-
Emergency/Disaster Recovery	nephele	-	-	E12	N/A	-	N/A	-	-	N/A
Remote Healthcare	nephele	H	-	N/A	-	-	-	-	-	-

Where “N/A” (not applicable) is shown in Table 3, this means that the MetaOS Use Case addresses a use case that was not included in the initial list of Considered Use Cases. While not corresponding to one of the Considered Use Cases, this mapping attempted to identify which architectural pattern was appropriate to the requirements.

5.1 Mapping Methodology

To evaluate how well our defined architectural patterns cover real-world scenarios, we compared them to the specific use cases presented by the MetaOS projects. This involved examining all 25 of their use cases and assessing their alignment with the 79 Considered Use Cases. While the MetaOS projects’ use cases may not encompass the entirety of real-world scenarios due to clustering challenges and the interdisciplinary nature of some cases, focusing on specific use cases is crucial for effective analysis. Seemingly similar use cases can differ significantly in solution complexity and technological requirements. For example, consider image recognition in computer vision: a fixed camera setup versus a dynamic environment with physically different cameras demands vastly different approaches and hardware.

As will be seen in Table 3, a given MetaOS Use Case can map to more than one of the Considered Use Cases, since the scope of most of the MetaOS Use Cases is defined more broadly, often including all the functional capabilities that the planned technology could address.

5.2 Analysis of Use Case Coverage

An examination of the 25 use cases reveals that most align well with the patterns outlined in Section 4. However, four use cases deviate from these patterns.

B2C Gaming and Entertainment (2 MetaOS Use Cases): These use cases might benefit from an additional architectural pattern, L7. This pattern prioritises service area or wide area coverage with robust “roaming” capabilities, less critical for the B2B scenarios that predominate among the Considered Use Cases.

Emergency Response (2 MetaOS Use Cases): Here, consider incorporating pattern L8. These scenarios, distinct from B2B or B2C, demand portability and self-sufficiency, independent from established infrastructure or networks.

Table 4 summarises how the MetaOS Use Cases map, or “cover”, the range of architectural patterns developed in this report. The first row (“Architectural Pattern matches”) presents the total number of distinct use cases that match each pattern. The second row (“Use Cases Match”) indicates how many of these distinct MetaOS use cases correspond to any of the Considered Use Cases described earlier in this report.

Coverage of Arch Patterns	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	L6	(new)L7	(new)L8
Architectural Pattern matches	8	14	16	12	11	15	2	2
Use cases matches	7	7	8	5	7	13	0	0
Use cases matches coverage	88%	50%	50%	42%	64%	87%	0%	0%

Table 4: MetaOS use cases mapping to different Architectural Patterns.

- ☁ Patterns L1 and L6 demonstrate particularly strong alignment with the use cases, with several use cases applicable to at least one of these patterns.
- ☁ Patterns L2, L3, and L6 exhibit the highest matching rate, with over 15 MetaOS use cases aligning with each. However, only half of the MetaOS use cases (50%) match L2 and L3.
- ☁ Use cases analyzed under L4 (Predictive Maintenance and Operational Reporting) show the lowest match rate (42%). This might be due to the inherent specificity of L4 use cases.

Table 5 organises the same information by industrial sector (Agriculture, Energy & Utilities, Manufacturing, Transport).

Coverage by Sector	A	E	M	T
Architectural Patterns matches	18	30	5	17
Use cases matches	12	18	5	10
Use cases matches coverage	67%	60%	100%	59%

Table 5: MetaOS use cases mapping by Sector

- ☁ Matching by sector shows a good fit with the current use cases. Nearly two-thirds of the Agriculture, Energy, and Transport sectors have matching use cases (67%, 60%, and 59% respectively). The Manufacturing sector exhibits a perfect match (100%).
- ☁ The Manufacturing sector demonstrates a perfect fit, but a significant number of use cases (7) in the Transport sector do not align with the current patterns. These may be related to traffic flow predictions.

6. Future Exploration

While the current architectural patterns provide a good foundation, some limitations arise. Here are some potential areas for exploration:

Expanding the scope: Consider if additional patterns might be beneficial to capture the nuances of use cases from different sectors or involving different data types (e.g., non-visual data in L2).

Implications of improved Gateway Interoperability: While our analysis focused on the core functionalities of the use cases, it is important to acknowledge the crucial role gateways play in all these projects. Given the increasing importance of interoperability between devices from different vendors, exploring a new architectural pattern that addresses the standardisation of gateway software stacks could be highly beneficial. Standardising these software stacks would simplify communication and data exchange between devices, regardless of the vendor. However, we recognize the inherent challenges in achieving such standardisation within a rapidly evolving domain. Similar to the emergence of the Matter protocol in the smart home environment – an industry-driven solution to device interoperability – the market itself might ultimately define the most suitable approach. Nevertheless, it is important to highlight that end-user demand for seamless vendor switching remains a key consideration. By exploring standardisation possibilities, we can contribute to a future where users are not locked into specific vendor ecosystems.

The document “Continuum Computing, More Than Cloud, Edge and IoT,” by Task Force 3 of the OpenContinuum project consortium, delves into the technical details and future plans for a unified Cloud-Edge-IoT architecture. While this summary focuses on the importance of a common language and building blocks, the full report explores the specific functionalities required by each block and details the next steps for designing a reference architecture. These next steps include refining the current taxonomy, finalising the reference architecture with workflows, and validating it with industry representatives.

Appendix 1: Preliminary Costs for Functional Components

All costs in Euros (€).

Gateway Investment Components

Gateway Base Unit

GBAS01	Base cost - fixed	500
GBAS02	Base cost - portable	250

	max gateway data rate (B/s)	
Gateway processing (based on gateway data rate)		
GDAT01	0.011	0
GDAT02	10,000	1,000
GDAT03	100,000,000	10,000
GDAT04	1,000,000,000,000	

	max gateway data rate (B/s)	
Gateway advanced processing (based on gateway data rate)		
GADV01	0.01	500
GADV02	10,000	2,000
GADV03	100,000,000	10,000
GADV04	1,000,000,000,000	

	max gateway data rate (B/s)	
Gateway base network cost (based on gateway data rate)		
GNB01	0.01	50
GNB02	10,000	200
GNB03	100,000,000	1,500
GNB04	1,000,000,000,000	3,000

	max gateway data rate (B/s)	
Gateway additional network cost for indoors/service area/service corridor (based on gateway data rate)		
GNF01	0.01	50
GNF02	10,000	100
GNF03	100,000,000	500
GNF04	1,000,000,000,000	1,000

	max device fanout	
Gateway - max connected device fanout (connected devices per gateway)		
GCAP01	10	0
GCAP02	100	300
GCAP03	1,000	2,000
GCAP04	10,000	10,000

Supports device actuation - based on max device fanout (actuated devices per gateway)	max device fanout	
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GACT01	10	50
GACT02	100	300
GACT03	1,000	2,000
GACT04	10,000	10,000
Supports regulated device actuation - added cost based on max device fanout (actuated devices per gateway)		
	max device fanout	
GREG01	10	50
GREG02	100	300
GREG03	1,000	2,000
GREG04	10,000	10,000

Support more than 1 kind of distributed device (device diversity)		
	Max # device types	
GDIV01	1	0
GDIV02	10	500
GDIV03	100	1,000
GDIV04	1,000	5,000

Device Investment Components

Device		
DBAS01	Base cost - fixed	25
DBAS02	Base cost - portable	25

Device Onboard Processing

DPROAE	aero	5,000
DPROFX	fixed	1,000
DPROCR	critical	5,000

Device processing (based on Device data rate)		
	max Device data rate (B/s)	
DDAT01	0.01	0
DDAT02	0.10	10
DDAT03	100	20
DDAT04	10,000	30
DDAT05	1,000,000	40
DDAT06	100,000,000	50
DDAT07	10,000,000,000	60
DDAT08	1,000,000,000,000	70

Device base network cost (based on Device data rate)	max Device data rate (B/s)	
DNB01	0.01	0
DNB02	0.10	100
DNB03	100	200
DNB04	10,000	300
DNB05	1,000,000	350
DNB06	100,000,000	400
DNB07	10,000,000,000	425
DNB08	1,000,000,000,000	450

Device additional network cost for indoors/service area/ service corridor (based on Device data rate)	max Device data rate (B/s)	
DNF01	0.01	5
DNF02	0.10	15
DNF03	100	20
DNF04	10,000	30
DNF05	1,000,000	40
DNF06	100,000,000	45
DNF07	10,000,000,000	50
DNF08	1,000,000,000,000	55

Supports actuation from device
DACT00 25

Supports actuation in a regulated environment (added
cost for regulatory certification)
DREG00 25

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